

The HuT

Consortium meetings

Deliverable D7.5

DEVELOPED WITHIN

WP7 Coordination and Management, T7.5 Consortium meetings

AUTHORS

Michele Calvello (UNISA); Alfonso Rossi Filangieri (UNISA)

Version 1.0

(28 November 2022)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101073957

1. Technical references

Project Acronym	The HuT
Project Title	The Human-Tech Nexus - Building a Safe Haven to cope with Climate Extremes
Project Coordinator	Michele Calvello UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI SALERNO mcalvello@unisa.it
Project Duration	October 2022 – September 2026 (48 months)
Deliverable No.	D7.5
Dissemination level*	PU
Work Package	WP7 - Coordination and Management
Task	T7.5 - Consortium meetings
Lead beneficiary	UNISA
Contributing beneficiary/ies	

- * PU = Public
PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

1.1. Document history

Version	Date	Lead contributor	Description
0.1	21.11.2022	Michele Calvello (UNISA)	First draft
0.2	24.11.2022	Guido Rianna (CMCC)	Critical review and proofreading
1.0	28.11.2022	Michele Calvello (UNISA)	Final version

2. Table of contents

1. Technical references	2
1.1. Document history	3
2. Table of contents	4
2.1. List of Tables	4
2.2. List of Figures	4
3. Kick-off Meeting (KoM) report	5
3.1. Location and participants	5
3.2. Agenda	8
DAY 1: Wednesday 12 October 2022	8
Afternoon session, 14:30-18:30	8
DAY 2: Thursday 13 October 2022	9
Morning session, 09:00-13:00	9
Lunch buffet, 13:00-14:30	9
Afternoon session, 14:30-18:30	10
Social dinner, 20:15-22:30	10
DAY 3: Friday 14 October 2022	11
Morning session, 09:00-12:30	11
Light packed lunch distributed to participants	11
Optional field visit to a site of DEM3 in the city of Sorrento, 14:30-16:00	11
3.3. Activities	12
3.3.1. Work Packages (WPs)	12
3.3.2. Preparatory phase	13

2.1. List of Tables

Table 1: Participant list	5
Table 2: First year deliverables (R=Document/report; DMP=Data management plan, PU=Public)	14
Table 3: Participants in General Assembly	15

2.2. List of Figures

none

3. Kick-off Meeting (KoM) report

3.1. Location and participants

The HuT KoM has been held in Sorrento (Italy) on October 12-14, 2022.

Table 1: Participant list

ID	Acronym	Name	Email
1	UNISA	Michele Calvello	mcalvello@unisa.it
1	UNISA	Alfonso Rossi Filangieri	arossifilangieri@unisa.it
1	UNISA	Gaetano Pecoraro	gpecoraro@unisa.it
1	UNISA	Settimio Ferlisi	sferlisi@unisa.it
1	UNISA	Paolo Capuano	pcapuano@unisa.it
1	UNISA	Maria Vittoria Gargiulo	mgargiulo@unisa.it
1	UNISA	Isadora Vida de Mefano e Silva	isadoramefano@gmail.com
1	UNISA	Rosa Menichini	rosamenichini93@gmail.com
2	CMCC	Guido Rianna	guido.rianna@cmcc.it
2	CMCC	Carmela De Vivo	carmela.devivo@cmcc.it
2	CMCC	Jose Maria Costa Saura	jmcostasaura@uniss.it
2	CMCC	Alfredo Reder	alfredo.reder@cmcc.it
2	CMCC	Costantino Battista Sirca	cosirca@uniss.it
2,1	CNR	Valentina Bacciu	Valentina.bacciu@ibe.cnr.it
3	HEREON	Jo-Ting Huang-Lachmann	jo-ting.huang-lachmann@hereon.de
3	HEREON	Anke Schluensen-Rico	anke.schluensen-rico@hereon.de
3	HEREON	Stefanie Truemper	stefanie.truemper@hereon.de
4	GFZ	Danijel Schorlemmer	ds@gfz-potsdam.de
4	GFZ	Laurens Oostwegel	laurens@gfz-potsdam.de
5	IIASA	Joanne Linnerooth-Bayer	bayer@iiasa.ac.at
5	IIASA	Florian KRAXNER	kraxner@iiasa.ac.at

6	UPC	Marcel Hurlimann	marcel.hurlimann@upc.edu
7	UPV	Javier Orozco-messana	jaormes@cst.upv.es
7	UPV	Adria Rubio-Martin	adrumar@cam.upv.es
7	UPV	Manuel Pulido-Velazquez	mapuve@hma.upv.es
8	NGI	Luca Piciullo	Luca.Piciullo@ngi.no
9	GWP-CEE	Anna Smetanova	anna.smetanova@gwpcee.org
10	HY	Sirkku Juhola	sirkku.juhola@helsinki.fi
11	IMO	Harpa Grímsdóttir	harpa@vedur.is
11	IMO	Anna Magdalena Muniak	muniak@vedur.is
12	VU	Gintautas Stankunavicius	gintas.stankunavicius@gf.vu.lt
12	VU	Egidijus Rimkus	egidijus.rimkus@gf.vu.lt
13	ARANTEC	Eisharc Jaquet	ejaquet@arantec.com
13	ARANTEC	Enrique Vidal	evidal@arantec.com
13	ARANTEC	Marta Carbonell	mcarbonell@arantec.com
14	KOTIVIZIG	Péter Gergő Katona Mr.	katona.peter@kotivizig.hu
14	KOTIVIZIG	Péter Sólyom	solyom.peter@kotivizig.hu
14	KOTIVIZIG	János Fehér	janos.feher@famife.hu
15	ICONS	Elisabeth Schmid	elisabeth.schmid@icons.it
15	ICONS	Ilaria Bonetti	ilaria.bonetti@icons.it
16	LEITHA	Antonio Tirri	antonio.tirri@leitha.eu
16	LEITHA	Francesco Asaro	francesco.asaro@live.it
16	LEITHA	Francesco Lo Conti	francesco.loconti@leitha.eu
17	SOR	Luigi Di Prisco	luigidiprisco82@libero.it
17	SOR	Massimo Coppola	mayor@comune.sorrento.na.it
18	CONF-NO	Francesca Cossu	francesca.cos@live.it
19	NIP	Ingibjorg Lilja Omarsdottir	ilo01@logreglan.is
20	MA	Erna Rakel Baldvinsdóttir	ernarakel@austurbru.is
21	UNIGE	Anna Scolobig	Anna.Scolobig@unige.ch
21	UNIGE	Mario Bruno Rohrer	Mario.Rohrer@unige.ch

22	UCL	Carina Fearnley	c.fearnley@ucl.ac.uk
22	UCL	Ilan Kelman	i.kelman@ucl.ac.uk
24	BGS	Katy Freeborough	karo@bgs.ac.uk
25	GNDR	Ipsita Sircar	ipsita.sircar@gndr.org
*	LAP	Manfred Staehli	manfred.staehli@wsl.ch
*	LAP (and MET)	Brian Golding	brian.golding@metoffice.gov.uk
*	LAP	Marleen de Rooter	m.c.de.rooter@vu.nl
*	LAP	Irene Amuron	amuron@climatecentre.org
*	LAP	Gavin White	Gavin.WHITE@ifrc.org
*	LEAP	Jonathan Pratschke	jonathan.pratschke@unina.it
*	LEAP	Cees van Westen	c.j.vanwesten@utwente.nl

Gavin White (member of The Hut legacy advisory panel, LAP) and Cees van Westen (member of the Legal and ethics advisory panel, LEAP) attended the meeting online.

3.2. Agenda

DAY 1: Wednesday 12 October 2022

Teatro Tasso, Piazza Sant'Antonino 25, Sorrento

Afternoon session, 14:30-18:30

The Partners meet the Partners

Start	End	What
14:30	14:50	Welcome address and institutional salutations Project Coordinator (UNISA) Mayor of Sorrento (SOR) Rector of University of Salerno (UNISA) Directors of involved departments: DICIV and DF (UNISA)
14:50	15:10	“The HuT” grant agreement by Michele Calvello (UNISA)
15:10	16:40	Project partners Short 3’ presentations By the 26 partners of the Consortium (Coordinator, 19 Beneficiaries, 1 Associated entity, 5 Associated partners)
16:40	17:00	COFFEE BREAK
17:00	18:30	Useful experiences 7’ pitches by Partners with examples of relevant achievements Impact-based forecasting (MET) Víz24 (KOTIVIZIG) Tools to cope with heatwaves (UPV) IoT monitoring activities (BGS) Real-time monitoring and data-visualization (NGI) Cloud Global Platform for Disaster Risk Reduction (ARANTEC) Climate proofing planning (CMCC) Narrative approaches supporting DRR and CCA (HEREON) Identification of vulnerabilities for effective decision-making (HY) The UN Warnings for All Initiative (UCL) GNDR initiatives (GNDR)

DAY 2: Thursday 13 October 2022

Teatro Tasso, Piazza Sant'Antonino 25, Sorrento

Morning session, 09:00-13:00

The Partners meet the Demonstrators

Start	End	What
09:00	10:40	Demonstrators
	(10')	DEM 1: Valencia city By Manuel Pulido-velazquez (UPV)
	(10')	DEM 2: Val d'Aran region By Marcel Hurlimann (UPC)
	(10')	DEM 3: Lattari mountains By Guido Rianna (CMCC)
	(10')	DEM 4: Vilnius city By Gintas Stankunavicius (VU)
	(10')	DEM 5: Schleswig- Holstein state and harbour cities By Jo-Ting Huang-Lachmann (HEREON)
	(10')	DEM 6: East fjords By Harpa Grímsdóttir (IMO)
	(10')	DEM 7: Hungarian Tisza River basin By Rátfai György (KOTIVIZIG)
	(10')	DEM 8: Ogliastra province By Valentina Bacciu (CNR)
	(10')	DEM 9: Dorset county By Katy Freeborough (BGS)
	(10')	DEM 10: Bern canton By Mario Rorer (UNIGE)
10:40	11:00	COFFEE BREAK
11:00	13:00	Internal Innovations Fair "Speed dating" with the demonstrators
	(45')	First group of DEMs
	(45')	Second group of DEMs
	(30')	Final round

Lunch buffet, 13:00-14:30

Afternoon session, 14:30-18:30

The Partners meet the WP Leaders

Start	End	What
14:30	16:30	Nexus and Arena Work Packages - Interactions One-to-one discussions on tasks and deliverables
	(60')	First group: WP2, WP3, WP4
	(60')	Second group: WP1, WP5
16:30	16:45	COFFEE BREAK
16:45	18:00	Nexus and Arena Work Packages – Plan of activities Presentations by WP Leaders
	(15')	WP2: Human behaviours, By Carina Fernley (UCL)
	(15')	WP3: Governance and policy, By Joanne Linneroth-Bayer (IIASA)
	(15')	WP4: Science and Technology, By Guido Rianna (CMCC)
	(15')	WP1: Demonstrators' arena, By Jo-Ting Huang-Lachmann (HEREON)
	(15')	WP5: Transferability and scalability, By Anna Smetanova (GWP-CEE)
18:00	18:30	De-briefing Feedback survey: individual activity for each partner

Social dinner, 20:15-22:30

DAY 3: Friday 14 October 2022

Teatro Tasso, Piazza Sant'Antonino 25, Sorrento

Morning session, 09:00-12:30

The Partners meet the world

Start	End	What
09:00	09:50	D & E & C measures
	(25')	WP6 communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy, By Ilaria Bonetti (ICONS) and Joanne Robbins (MET)
	(25')	Discussion: Identify relevant conferences and events for the 1 st year of The HuT
09:50	10:30	Legacy Advisory Panel
	(25')	Short 5' introductory presentations By the 5 members of LAP Manfred Staehli (LandAware) Brian Golding (HIWeather) Marleen de Ruiter (RiskKAN) Irene Amuron (Anticipation Hub) Gavin White (REAP)
	(15')	Discussion
10:30	10:50	COFFEE BREAK
10:50	11:10	Expectations from the REA during the project and Synergy with other DRS EU funded projects By Antonio Fernandez-Ranada Shaw (The HuT EU project officer)
11:10	11:35	Legacy and Ethics Advisory Panel
	(15')	Short 5' introductory presentations By the 3 members of LEAP Jonathan Pratschke (University of Napoli Federico II, Italy) Cees van Westen (University of Twente, Netherlands) Emilia Garda (Politecnico di Torino, Italy)
	(10')	Discussion
11:35	11:50	Financial and administration issues Q&A with Project Manager Alfonso Rossi Filangieri (UNISA)
11:50	12:30	General Assembly Feedback on Kick-off Meeting and outlook for the next 12 months

Light packed lunch distributed to participants

Optional field visit to a site of DEM3 in the city of Sorrento, 14:30-16:00

Vallone dei Mulini

3.3. Activities

The Meeting started with an overview of the project given by the Coordinator. All the activities listed in the Agenda have been carried out

The presentations and the video recordings of all the sessions are available, with the consent of the speakers, at the following Google Drive folders

- 12 October 14 30-15 10 (Introduction)
<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1YVda2ftArVm0wvBOdbmmzsruFcyDWCcd>
- 12 October 15 10-16 40 (Project Partners)
<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/14Adef1UqE96NC2dr0QD9zH5Zi3qi0Omw>
- 12 October 17 00-18 30 (Useful experiences)
https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/173zL_50OHFywEXDYaxymd7Qpv4LJHB7H
- 13 October 09 00-10 40 (Demonstrators)
<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1bsdcwQOchUHrsSkEV5Jywx9FT5RBOldO>
- 13 October 16 45-18 00 (Nexus and Arena Work Packages)
https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1trllcTmrvb0Py_sn3KvhkLI1t-dlXT8GC
- 14 October 09 00-12 30 (Communication, LAP, REA)
https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1xiiFsFcO68BzvtjRZ_KgAMPsh-NqMmK9
- Video recordings
https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1gKO_sO6B4rBTIHBfMPeq5rfGvK2cL2LS

3.3.1. Work Packages (WPs)

All the activities that will be conducted in the seven WPs were presented in the KoM.

Work package WP1 – Demonstrators’ arena. It was presented and discussed in the second day of the meeting, in the sessions “The Partners meet the Demonstrators” and “The Partners meet the WP Leaders”. The first session included presentations from the 10 demonstrators and an Internal Innovations Fair (nicknamed “Speed dating” with the demonstrators) during which all the participants had the opportunity to discuss in detail possibilities of cooperation, transferability of innovations and exchange by means of joint actions. During the second session, WP1 Leader delivered a presentation and conducted one-to-one discussions on tasks and deliverables with the other participants of the WP.

Work package WP2 – Human behaviours. It was presented and discussed in the afternoon of the second day of the meeting, in the session “The Partners meet the WP Leaders”. During this session, WP2 Leader delivered a presentation and conducted one-to-one discussions on tasks and deliverables with the other participants of the WP.

Work package WP3 – Governance and policy. It was presented and discussed in the afternoon of the second day of the meeting, in the session “The Partners meet the WP Leaders”. During

this session, WP3 Leader delivered a presentation and conducted one-to-one discussions on tasks and deliverables with the other participants of the WP.

Work package WP4 – Science and Technology. It was presented and discussed in the afternoon of the second day of the meeting, in the session “The Partners meet the WP Leaders”. During this session, WP4 Leader delivered a presentation and conducted one-to-one discussions on tasks and deliverables with the other participants of the WP.

Work package WP5 – Transferability and scalability. It was presented and discussed in the afternoon of the second day of the meeting, in the session “The Partners meet the WP Leaders”. During this session, WP5 Leader delivered a presentation and conducted one-to-one discussions on tasks and deliverables with the other participants of the WP.

Work package WP6 – Communication, dissemination and exploitation. It was presented and discussed in the third day of the meeting, in the session “The Partners meet the world”. During this session, WP6 Leader delivered a presentation and chaired a discussion mainly centered around identifying relevant conferences and events for the 1st year of The HuT.

Work package WP7 – Coordination and Management. It was presented and discussed in the third day of the meeting, in the session “The Partners meet the world”. During this session, the EU Project Officer assigned to The HuT delivered a presentation and the Project Manager chaired a Q&A with the participants on financial and administration issues.

3.3.2. Preparatory phase

A timetable of research and administration tasks through which the project activities for the first year has been discussed.

The coordinator will make available the procedure for the deliverable revision, deliverable templates, and the other templates that will be needed during the project life.

All the project documents will be shared among the participants by means of a shared Google Drive, wherein folders and subfolders will be created with the following structure:

- main shared directory (read-only access granted to all the participants);
- one folder, and nested sub-folders when needed, for each Demonstrator (editing rights for the demonstrator leader);
- one folder, and nested sub-folders when needed, for each Work Package (editing rights for the work package leader);
- one folder, and nested sub-folders when needed, for each consortium meeting (editing rights for main organizers);
- one folder and a series of sub-folders for the deliverables (editing rights for lead contributors and reviewers);
- specific folders, whenever needed.

DELIVERABLES

The content of the deliverables and the time schedule are contained in the Grant Agreement. Table 2 shows the Deliverables of the first year of the project.

Table 2: First year deliverables (R=Document/report; DMP=Data management plan, PU=Public)

No.	Name	WP	Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination level	Due date (month)
D7.5	Consortium meetings	WP7	1 - UNISA	R	PU	2
D1.4	'The Hut for Me and You'	WP1	21 - UNIGE	R	PU	3
D7.1	Project management Plan	WP7	1 - UNISA	R	PU	3
D7.4	Ethical requirements Plan	WP7	1 - UNISA	R	PU	3
D1.3	Architecture of demonstrator's data portal	WP1	8 - NGI	R	PU	6
D2.1	SoA on Human-centric DRR activities	WP2	22 - UCL	R	PU	6
D4.1	SoA on prevention and preparedness DRR actions	WP4	2 - CMCC	R	PU	6
D6.1	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of results	WP6	15 - ICONS	R	PU	6
D7.2	Data management Plan	WP7	1 - UNISA	DMP	PU	6
D7.3	Risk management Plan	WP7	1 - UNISA	R	PU	6
D4.2	Monitoring activities to be developed in the Demonstrators	WP4	13 - ARANTEC	R	PU	8
D4.5	Modelling activities to be developed in the Demonstrators	WP4	1 - UNISA	R	PU	9
D1.1	Ongoing activities in the demonstrators	WP1	3 - HEREON	R	PU	11
D1.2	Composition of Local DRR nexus Forums	WP1	3 - HEREON	R	PU	12
D1.5	'The Hut for Me and You' narratives	WP1	3 - HEREON	R	PU	12
D5.1	Approaches to transfer DRR innovations	WP5	9 - GWP-CEE	R	PU	12
D5.2	Documenting DRR solutions and the transfer processes	WP5	9 - GWP-CEE	R	PU	12
D5.3	Minutes from I-DRRnF workshops	WP5	21 - UNIGE	R	PU	12

The PM will check the status of the deliverable preparation, with each responsible partner, in order to ensure a timely submission, also taking into account the revision process.

MEETINGS

The First Annual Meeting will be held in Valencia (Spain), held by UPV. The other scheduled annual meetings will be held in: Switzerland, held by UNIGE; Germany, held by HEREON; Italy, led by CMCC.

GENERAL ASSEMBLY

The General Assembly was held on Friday 14 October 2022, during the third day of the KoM. Table 3 shows the list of participants.

Table 3: Participants in General Assembly

Partner	Name	Participation
UNISA	Michele Calvello	yes
CMCC	Guido Rianna	yes
HEREON	Jo-Ting Huang-Lachmann	yes
GFZ	Danijel Schorlemmer	yes
IIASA	Joanne Linnerooth-Bayer	yes
UPC	Marcel Hurlimann	yes
UPV	Manuel Pulido-Velazquez	yes
NGI	Luca Piciullo	yes
GWP-CEE	Anna Smetanova	yes
HY	Sirkku Juhola	no
IMO	Harpa Grímsdóttir	yes
VU	Gintautas Stankunavicius	yes
ARANTEC	Eisharc Jaquet	yes
KOTIVIZIG	György Rátfai	yes (Janos Feher)
ICONS	Ilaria Bonetti	yes
LEITHA	Antonio Tirri	yes
SOR	Luigi Di Prisco	no
CONF-NO	Francesca Cossu	yes

NIP	Ingibjorg Lilja Omarsdottir	yes
MA	Tinna Kristbjorg Halldorsdottir	yes (Erna Raket Baldvinsdóttir)
UNIGE	Markus Stoffel	no
UCL	Carina Fearnley	yes
MET	Joanne Robbins	yes (Brian Golding)
BGS	Katy Freeborough	yes
GNDR	Hepi Rahmawati	yes (Ipsita Sircar)

The General Assembly has officially appointed the following.

Project Management Team:

1. Michele Calvello, coordinator, UNISA
2. Guido Rianna, deputy coordinator, CMCC
3. Alfonso Rossi Filangieri, project manager, UNISA
4. Carina Fearnley, UCL
5. Jo-Ting Huang-Lachmann (HEREON)

The Hut legacy advisory panel - LAP

1. Manfred Staehli
2. Brian Golding
3. Marleen de Rooter
4. Irene Amuron
5. Gavin White

Legal and ethics advisory panel - LEAP

1. Jonathan Pratschke
2. Cees van Westen

